

Jadidchilikda islom diniga munosabat

Отношение к исламу в джадидизме

Attitude to Islam in Jadidism

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Abstract: this article talks about important processes, changes in spirituality and globalization that have influenced Islam.

Key words: Sciences, education, religious education, justice, dignity, fairness, value.

Jadidism, or Jadidiyat, is a social, political and spiritual movement uniquely formed in Islam. Jadidism is an idea and leadership that found its place in the period from the end of the 19th to the beginning of the 20th century and created new movements of Islam.

The main goal of Jadidism is to ensure that the religion of Islam corresponds to its time and modernity, to retrain and change its basic information and principles. The goal of this movement is to adapt religious disciplines and practices to the demands of the modern world by introducing systematic changes in the fundamental rules, forms and practices of Islam..

Jadidism requires the development of Islamic education, science, social issues, social rights and other areas. In this movement, the religion of Islam requires the use of modern science and technology, changing the social environment, maintaining social justice and changing some social problems.

The main features of Jadidism are to re-examine the unique structure of Islam in its time and in its environment, adapt it to social development and modernity, adapt religious rules to socio-legal problems, and be the voice of Muslims in social life. and the political environment includes goals such as ensuring Thus, Jadidism ensures the successful interaction of antiquity and modernity in Islam itself, between preserving religious rules and adapting to the demands of the modern world. Jadidism seeks to adapt the Islamic religion to modernity in its own way, without changing its details.

Jadidism, or Jadidiyat, is a social, political and spiritual movement uniquely formed in Islam. Jadidism is an idea and leadership that found its place in the period from the end of the 19th to the beginning of the 20th century and created new movements of Islam. Jadidism in Islam emphasizes the importance of interpreting books such as the Qur'an and Hadith within a historical and social context. It encourages scholars and intellectuals to approach religious teachings with critical thinking, taking into account the changing conditions and needs of modern society.

Jadidism requires the development of Islamic education, science, social issues, social rights and other areas. In this movement, the religion of Islam requires the use of modern science and technology, changing the social environment, maintaining social justice and changing some social problems.

The main features of Jadidism are to re-examine the unique structure of Islam in its time and in its environment, adapt it to social development and modernity, adapt religious rules to socio-legal problems, and be the voice of Muslims in social life and political environment. Thus, Jadidism ensures a successful interaction between antiquity and modernity in Islam itself, between the preservation of religious rules and adaptation to the requirements of the modern world. Jadidism, without changing the details of Islam, strives in its own way to adapt it to modern times.

Jadidism may have the following effects on Islamic educational systems:

Updating educational methods and methodologies. The main content of “Jadidlik” is the desire to update and develop educational methods and methodologies. Jadidists are those who seek teaching methods based on scientific research. These methods incorporate innovation and interactivity to help students improve their understanding and knowledge. Teaching methods, curricula and pedagogical methods can be updated to take into account the influence of Jadidism in Islamic educational systems.

News in the field of science and research: Jadidism can bring news in the field of science and research in Islamic education systems. Jadidists strive to enrich students' knowledge with new information, historical approaches, and ideas based on scientific research. It plays an important role in providing students with additional knowledge and information while focusing on the basics of Islam.

Education and spiritual-educational development: Jadidism places great emphasis on education and spiritual-educational development in Islamic educational systems. They strive to enhance the spiritual and educational values of students, ensure their personal development and provide students with a spiritual path based on Islamic values such as justice, kindness, literature, ethics, etc.

Socio-historical knowledge of students. The influence of Jadidism on educational systems was aimed at increasing the socio-historical knowledge of students. They

sought to provide students with scientific knowledge on topics such as historical events, social structure, human rights, social entities, government and legal systems. This helps develop students' understanding of the world and gives them a socio-historical understanding. This manifests itself in improving historical understanding and updating educational methods and techniques. This influence will be important for the development of Islamic educational systems, focusing students' attention on the fundamentals of Islam and preparing them for life in the modern world.

Summary

The main goal of Jadidism is to ensure that the religion of Islam corresponds to its time and modernity, to retrain and change its basic information and principles. The goal of this movement is to adapt religious sciences and practices to the demands of the modern world by introducing systematic changes in the basic rules, forms and practices of Islam.

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